

Synthesis and Biological Activities of some Substituted Pyrazolylmethylene-1,2,4-triazoles, -1,3,4-thiadiazoles and -1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1*H*-4-pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (2) on treatment with aldehydes give the *N*-benzylidene derivatives (3a-g). The hydrazide (2) reacts either with acetylacetone or with ethyl acetoacetate to give 1-[3,5-dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl]acetyl-3-methyl-1*H*-pyrazoles (6, 7). Compound 2 on treatment with isothiocyanates give *N*-[3,5-dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl] acetyl thiosemicarbazides (8a-d), which undergo cyclisation under different conditions to give the corresponding substituted [3,5-dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl] methylene-1,2,4-triazoles (9a-d), -1,3,4-thiadiazoles (10a-d) and -1,3,4-oxadiazoles (11a-d). The compounds have been tested for their biological activity.

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PYRAZOLE derivatives have attracted much attention due to their diverse biological properties¹. The incorporation of 1*H*-pyrazole is of particular interest as some of the compounds with this system possess enhanced biological activities². Various substituted 1,2,4-triazoles and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were synthesised and their biological activities studied.

(4-nitrophenyl)-1*H*-4-pyrazoleacetate³ (1). The 4-pyrazoleacetate (1) on reaction with hydrazine hydrate gave the hydrazide (2), which when further reacted with various aldehydes, gave the *N*-benzylidene derivatives (3a-g; Scheme 1). Compound 2 was reacted with acetylacetone or ethyl acetoacetate to give the corresponding hydrazones (4, 5), which on treatment with acid got cyclised to the *N*-acetylpyrazoles (6, 7). Alternatively, 6 and 7 were directly obtained when the reaction was carried out in AcOH (Scheme 2).

- (a) R = Ph
- (b) 2-NO₂C₆H₄
- (c) 4-NO₂C₆H₄
- (d) 4-MeC₆H₄
- (e) 2-OHC₆H₄
- (f) 4-OMeC₆H₄
- (g) 2-Furyl

Scheme 1

Ethyl 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate was reacted with 4-nitrophenylhydrazine to give ethyl 3,5-dimethyl-1-

Scheme 2

The hydrazide (2) was reacted with KSCN in the presence of acid to give the corresponding thiosemicarbazide⁴ (8a). Similarly, 2 was treated with various arylisothiocyanates to give the *N*-substituted-thiosemicarbazides (8b-d), which when treated with NaOH gave the corresponding substituted 1,2,4-triazoles⁵ (9a-d). The treatment of 8a-d with concentrated H₂SO₄ yielded the corresponding 1,3,4-thiadiazoles⁶ (10a-d), while the treatment of 8a-d with I₂ solution resulted in the formation of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles⁷ (11a-d; Scheme 3).

Biological activity: Compounds 3-13 were evaluated for their biological activity *in vitro*

Scheme 3

against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at 2 mg ml⁻¹ and 5 mg ml⁻¹ in the nutrient agar media following the Ditch-plate method⁶. Compound 8a inhibited the growth of all the bacteria at the concentration levels of 5 and 2 mg ml⁻¹. Compounds 7, 8a and 8d inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* and *S. typhi* at the concentration of 5 mg ml⁻¹. Compounds 9a, 10a only inhibited the growth of *E. coli*, and 11a only inhibited the growth of *S. aureus*. The rest of the compounds were not significantly active against all the bacteria.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer, downfield from TMS as an internal reference.

Ethyl 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-4-pyrazoleacetate¹ (1): A solution of ethyl 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate (0.01 mol) and 4-nitrophenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in AcOH (20 ml) was refluxed for 12 h. The cooled reaction mixture was then poured into ice-water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol (Table 1).

3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-4-pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (2): To a solution of the 4-pyrazoleacetate (1; 0.1 mol) in ethanol (80 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.15 mol) was added. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath at 60–70° for 12 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol as a white crystalline compound (Table 1): 1 ν_{max} (KBr) 1660 (amide C=O), 1580 (NO₂) and 3100–3380 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 3.78 (2H, s, CH₃), 2.38–2.4 (6H, d, CH₃), 10.0–10.2 (1H, br, NH), 5.8 (2H, s, NH₂) and 7.4–7.8 (4H, m, ArH).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1–7^a

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1		112 ^a	74	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
2		237	71	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃
3a	Ph	198	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃
3b	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	202	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅
3c	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	292	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅
3d	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	221	55	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃
3e	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	255	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄
3f	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	155	58	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄
3g	2-Furyl	242	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
4	Me	109	78	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄
5	OEt	105	76	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅
6	Me	114	74	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃
7	OH	158	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄

^aCompounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses, ^bLit.¹ 111–12°.

N-Arylidene-3,5-dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-4-pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (3a–g): To 4-pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (2; 0.001 mol) dissolved in ethanol (12 ml) was added an appropriate aldehyde (0.001 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h and the resulting solid separated on cooling was recrystallised from methanol (Table 1).

The hydrazone (4, 5): To a solution of 4-pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (2; 0.05 mol) in ethanol (15 ml), was added either ethyl acetoacetate or acetylacetone (0.05 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h, left overnight at 0° and the resulting solid was washed with cold ethanol and crystallised from ethanol-DMF mixture (Table 1): 5 (R=OEt) ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (ester C=O), 1665 (amide C=O), 3260 (NH), 1620 (C=N) and 1580 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

1-[3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl] acetyl-3-methyl-1H-5-substituted-pyrazole (6, 7). **Method 1**: The hydrazones (4, 5; 0.005 mol) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and to it was added catalytic amount of concentrated HCl. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h, cooled and poured into ice. The separated solid was then washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Method 2: 4-Pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (2; 0.05 mol) and either acetylacetone or ethyl acetoacetate (0.05 mol) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, cooled and poured over ice. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1): 7 (R=OH) ν_{max} (KBr) 1645, 1675(C=O), 1610(C=N) and 1580 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.43 (9H, t, 3 × CH₃), 5.8 (1H, s, OH), 3.79 (2H, s, CH₂) and 6.7–7.85 (5H, m, ArH and C₄-H).

[3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-pyrazole-4-yl] acetylthiosemicarbazide (8a): To a solution of pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (2; 0.003 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added potassium thiocyanate (0.0035 mol) followed by a few drops of HCl. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath at

70–80° for 3 h, concentrated, cooled and the separated solid was washed with cold methanol and recrystallised from methanol (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 8a–11d*

Compd. no.	R	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
8a	H	233	67	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S
8b	Ph	202	60	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S
8c	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	186	50	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S
8d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	182	53	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ SCl
9a	H	121	52	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S
9b	Ph	297	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S
9c	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	232	58	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S
9d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	252	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ SCl
10a	H	108	40	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S
10b	Ph	94	46	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S
10c	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	209	43	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S
10d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	210	43	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ SCl
11b	Ph	118	40	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S
11c	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	221	35	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S
11d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	251	38	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ Cl

*Compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

[3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-pyrazole-4-yl] acetyl-substituted-thiosemicarbazides (8b–d) : To a solution of 4-pyrazoleacetic acid hydrazide (2 ; 0.003 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added aryliso-thiocyanate (0.0035 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, cooled and the separated solid was washed with ether and crystallised from methanol (Table 2) : 8d (R=4-ClC₆H₄) $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 665 (amide C=O), 1 180 (thioamide C=S), 3 180, 3 350 (NH) and 1 580 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

3-[3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl] methylene-4-substituted-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiol (9a–d) : To a solution of substituted-thiosemicarbazide (8a–d ; 0.001 mol) was added NaOH (2N ; 18 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with cold dilute HCl and the separated solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from methanol (Table 2) : 9b (R=Ph) $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 480 (SH), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 580 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

2-[3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl] methylene-5-substituted-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (10a–d) : Substituted-thiosemicarbazides (8a–d ; 0.001 mol) was added in portion to concentrated H₂SO₄ (10 ml) at 0° and stirred for 1 h maintaining the temperature at 0°. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand for 20 h at room temperature,

poured over crushed ice with stirring and the separated solid was washed with dilute NH₃ solution followed by washing with water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

2-[3,5-Dimethyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl] methylene-5-substituted-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole (11a–d) : To a solution of substituted-thiosemicarbazides (8a–d ; 0.002 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was added cold NaOH (4N ; 5 ml) and I₂ in potassium iodide (5% solution) dropwise till the colour of I₂ persisted at 0–5°. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath, allowed to stand overnight at room temperature, poured over crushed ice and the precipitated solid was washed with dilute sodium thiosulphate solution followed by washing with water and crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture (Table 2) : 11d (R=4-ClC₆H₄) $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 360 (NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 585 cm⁻¹ (NO₂) ; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.73 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.4 (6H, d, 2×CH₃), 10.1–10.3 (1H, br, NH) and 7.4–7.9 (8H, m, ArH).

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